

Acknowledgement

The authors desire to express their thanks to Dr. S. K. Agarwal, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow and Dr. T. R. Govindachari, Ciba Research Centre, Bombay for elemental analysis and various spectra. Grateful acknowledgement is made to SCSIR, Lucknow, India for grant of scholarship to one of us.

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Chemical examination of seeds of *Amomum subulatum*

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Manuscript received 9 June 1975; revised 26 March 1976;
accepted 30 March 1976.

AMOMUM subulatum (family Zingiberaceae).
Uses—Medicinal¹. *Previous work*—Ash contents of seeds². *Present work*—Powdered seeds were extracted with hot petroleum ether (40°–60°), then successively with cold methanolic hydrochloric acid (2%), ethylacetate and hot alcohol.

The petroleum ether extract gave viscous oil, hence was rejected. The 2% cold methanolic extract on column chromatography over silica gel followed by paper chromatography yielded compound A. The concentrated ethylacetate and ethanolic extracts both gave a creamish white deposit which on chromatography over silica gel yielded compound B along with few minor substances.

From a study of u.v. spectral data, degradation, m.p., m.m.p. the compound A, C₂₈H₃₃O₁₇, m.p. > 300° was identified as petunidin 3,5-diglucoside and the compound B, C₂₁H₂₄O₁₂, m.p. 230° (dec.) was identified as Leucocyanidin-3-O-β-D-glucopyranoside. Studies on minor substances are in progress.

Acknowledgement

The authors desire to express their thanks to Dr. S. K. Agarwal, Central Drug Research Institute,

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Lucknow and Dr. T. R. Govindachari, Ciba Research Centre, Bombay for elemental analyses and for recording spectra. Grateful acknowledgement is made to SCSIR, Lucknow, India for the grant of scholarship to one of us.

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Lead-*n*-butyl thioglycolate complexes—A polarographic study

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Manuscript received 1 October 1975; revised 30 March 1976;
accepted 30 March 1976.

IN this communication, composition and stability constants of Pb²⁺-*n*-butyl thioglycolate complexes have been investigated in 50% dimethyl formamide (D.M.F.) media polarographically. The values of ΔG, ΔH and ΔS are also reported.

Experimental

n-Butyl thioglycolate (referred herein as RSH) was supplied by Evan's Chemetics Inc., N.Y. and all other chemicals were AnalaR (B.D.H.). Freshly prepared solutions of the ligand and others were used to avoid the effect of ageing and air oxidation. NaClO₄ and Triton X-100 were used as supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor respectively. All solutions used for recording polarograms had in addition to RSH, a lead ion concentration of 1.00 mM, 0.1M NaClO₄ and 0.002% triton X-100 in 50% D.M.F. media. The entire study was carried out at a constant ionic strength μ = 0.1M NaClO₄ and at a pH 4.30 ± 0.04 maintained by adding 5.00 ml of Clark's and Lub's buffer of pH 4.2. The concentration of RSH varied from 0.004 to 0.012M.

A manual polarograph in conjunction with a thermostated H-cell was used for recording the polarograms against S.C.E. as a reference electrode in an inert atmosphere of nitrogen. The capillary had the following characteristics

$$m = 1.107 \text{ mg/sec.}, t = 4.85 \text{ sec. at } -0.3 \text{ Volt vs. S.C.E.}$$

Results and Discussion

The plot of i_d vs. $h^{1/2} t_{eff}$ yielded a straight line showing the diffusion controlled nature of the waves.

The plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_d - i}$ vs. $E_{d.e.}$ were also linear whose